

THE ROLE OF PSYCHOLOGY IN ARCHITECTURE

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Annotation.

Knowing the principles and possibilities of the psychological impact of architecture and design on the human mind, the urgent need for individual design has reached the level of demand in society. Researchers in the field of architecture and those working in this field take into account the impact of the constructions on people, and in this case refer to human psychology.

Key words.

Environmental psychology, emotions, behavior, ideal environments, visual illusion, haptic, colors and lights, conference halls, typology, mind, physical environment, personality and dispositional factors, psychological processes, well-being, unity, legibility, mystery, complexity.

What distinguishes a space as a specific typology? What segregates it? It's the design, both inside and outside, our perception, and the response of five senses to the space. Why does a home, anywhere in the world look like home? Or an office like an office? Or a hospital like a hospital and a school like a school? Based on standard design guidelines, we design a house, office, hospital, or school, that fits into the respective typology. Our mind then begins to imagine that space that has been fitted in our minds.

A key notion proven by centuries of evidence is that our human behavior adapts to environments and factors at that specific point in time, better known as architectural psychology. Knowing that our ancestors built pyramids, palaces, and lived in extreme weather conditions without the technologies available today, it's evident that the built environment is constantly modified based on human needs (food, climatic comfort, shelter, space) and an individual person's needs (factors that affect the role individuals play in society) for the population at the

time. Human reaction to their built environment can be influenced by tweaking and balancing certain factors to impact movement and interaction in a space.

Psychology of Architecture is also known as Environmental Psychology. Environmental psychology is an interdisciplinary field that focuses on the interplay between individuals and their surroundings. The field defines the term environment broadly, encompassing natural environments, social settings, built environments, learning environments, and informational environments.

"Many people tend to underestimate the contribution of the physical environment to their overall level of life satisfaction. There is also a tendency to explain psychological processes exclusively in terms of personality and dispositional factors while ignoring environmental and situational factors. Nevertheless, the current scientific literature is confirming the profound impact that one's physical environment can have on thoughts, emotions, and behaviour.

*The study of these interactions between humans and their physical environment is referred to in many different ways, but most frequently as Architectural Psychology. Strictly speaking, it is neither architecture nor psychology, but a unique field that combines relevant theoretical aspects of both in order to enhance the human experience. Architectural Psychology effectively bridges the gap between architecture and psychology."*⁹⁵

Ideal Environments. Architecture can evoke a sense of awe, well-being or instill the desire to leave a space if it makes us feel unwelcome or uncomfortable. Places, where people feel safe and self-assured, are Ideal Environments. These are the spaces where they are comfortable and familiar and are engaging.

There are four factors that determine whether an environment is ideal:

1. Unity: the sense that people and environment function in collaboration with each other.
2. Legibility: the assumption that people can navigate the environment without getting lost.
3. Mystery: the expectation of being able to acquire more information regarding the environment people are in.
4. Complexity: the amount of information and variety in the surrounding that makes people eager and inquisitive.

A well-designed space will make a person feel safe and connected to others, have the ability to freely move around offer an appropriate amount of sensory stimulation. Spaces should be designed in a way that they provide the people with

⁹⁵ Dr. Morgan Williams
(Licensed Clinical Psychologist & Licensed Architect)

a welcoming experience that inspires them and allows them to just be in the moment.

Our senses respond to those spaces right by thinking about it and begin to form adjectives for it, like – cozy house, smelly hospital, lit office, huge classrooms, etc. When we enter a space, all our five senses get engaged with each other and thus we respond to the space. Haptics, the sense of touch conveys the length, depth, mass, and texture through legs, feet, hands, and body mass to our brains. In this sense, we need to understand that sight is the dominant sense among all and humans define architecture through its appealing form. The space through the rest of the senses is perceived consciously or unconsciously. Despite that, our other four senses store in the memory the nature of the space and reaction to it that is seldom perceived by the eyes. This creates visual illusion within the users and so humans in most cases define the space purely based on this visual illusion, i.e. form and shape of the building. Haptics also identify poor ventilation and temperature that gives us discomfort. Consciously or subconsciously our skin reacts to this which sends signals to our brain and we tend to focus less on our respective work. Hearing as well as the sense of smell also sends similar responses to the brain which then impacts our respective work.

The perceived form, material, texture, smell, and sound collected by our senses are stored in the form of memory and are recollected when we come in contact with similar space, especially of a particular typology again. When all our five senses are allowed to interact with each other, i.e. when architecture for the senses is designed, we tend to be more comfortable and thus we interact with the space. This communication is important for keeping the user bound to live in the ‘present’ and constantly engaged with the surrounding.

Colors and lights too are as much as important as other features in the space. They are stored in our memory in the same way as other sensual perceptions. Various studies have shown that colors affect our psychological behavior and hence many color psychologists are working in integration with architects. For example, blue is said to increase creativity, red reminds us of danger letting us give importance to the details of a respective problem, whereas white creates a peaceful atmosphere. Colors can even have cultural or religious significance and based on this, we even categorize the space or a place. We also respond to colors based on our past experience, whether good or bad. The more the colors in a structure, the more joyous and comfortable we tend to be. Also, lighting, if well designed can create a joyous environment, but too much illumination, e.g. in offices, after long periods causes stress and fear of revisiting the space.

The psychology of color plays a vital role in arousing the emotions of the users. Designers believe that architecture is an act of communication, and the color is the medium that will articulate the message.

Emergency areas in hospital rooms are often encapsulated in green drapes as this color evokes a sense of calmness. Restaurants and food chains typically instil a red color scheme as a subtle marketing strategy. Red attracts attention, stimulates appetite and induces hunger.

Conference halls are often specified with warm, earthy hues like brown and orange as they promote social connection. White denotes innocence, cleanliness and purity. Combined with a heightened ceiling, it exudes a welcoming aura as opposed to the claustrophobic effect of dark or small spaces.

Another example is of a house. The word itself induces a feeling of coziness and security and is welcoming. But if the interiors are designed according to the design of an office, we tend to hesitate to live in it because of the stored memory of an office space or residential space. On the other hand, spaces also promote physical as well as mental well-being. It is also the main factor that helps us distinguish contemplation, religious spaces, and health spas from the rest, i.e., industrial, malls and offices, houses, schools, etc.

As said in the introduction paragraph, our minds also 'habitually' respond to space. Given that it is designed according to the standards, our perception of the space, be it school, office, or hospital is automatic. We form a mental map of that space or a building, which is why, unless the spatial planning or design of the particular typology is designed differently, we generally tend to know the space.

⁹⁶ <https://sahidzarafshon.com/conference/>

⁹⁷ <https://www.google.com/url?sa=i&url=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.meetings-conventions.com%2FMeeting-Event-Venues%2FTashkent-Uzbekistan%2FConvention-Hotel%2FHilton-Tashkent-City-p54549906&psig=AOvVaw2QPWLJOUyzOawU8Qd0aqYf&ust=1679108548061000&source=images&cd=vfe&ved=0CBAQjhXqFwoTCKCJ5vX84f0CFQAAAAAdAAAAABAE>

All our senses collect it in the form of memory and when spatial planning is different than that we are habitual to, our senses get confused and so does our behavioral pattern. We react to this new space either positively or negatively. Both these responses to the particular space or typology build a space in our memory, which is recollected the other time we visit.

A negative response may lead to dissatisfaction and restlessness. An example of this is the hospital typology, where we already know about the space even before visiting. This can sometimes be dangerous and can cause anxiety within the patient, and as the mind too affects physical well-being, this anxiety can interrupt the process of faster recovery within him or her. Designing for the senses in this typology thus becomes important for the overall well-being of the patient. Positive response induces energy, joy, creativity, and calmness and so we tend to visit that place again and again. Contemplation centers, healthcare resorts, outdoor areas like nature, and landscaped gardens give us calmness. Certain restaurants, if well designed induce joy and creativity in us. In this case, we need to remember that humans, apart from being social, are also inclined towards nature and being holistic. This is the reason that we humans become calm when we are in nature.

Spaces can create a sense of security, danger, calmness, comfort, frustration, fear, anxiety, depression, creativity, conspiracy, and so on within the users. Architecture can thus play a significant role in shaping our thinking, actions, performance, moods and behavior, and also our social interaction and overall health. But in the era of competitions and aesthetics, we seldom give attention to designing for humans that affect his or her psychology.

Conclusion. We never know how better can an industry grow but including humanism, social life and the environment in any sector could develop an industry to grow better, hence if we want to make this field of architecture and interior design, we should develop spaces and facades carefully keeping in mind the resources, the people residing and the surroundings to meet their comfort, seek luxury in vision and is functionally adaptable.

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